

Physics-Informed Neural Networks for Quantitative Analysis of Medical CT scans

Mr. Stevan Vrbaški, Research Assistant, Department of General Educational Subjects, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad

Recent advances in computed tomography (CT) imaging have introduced spectral CT, enabling not just anatomical but also quantitative analysis of tissue properties. Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) are at the forefront of leveraging these capabilities to go beyond traditional Hounsfield unit measurements, providing deeper insights into tissue characteristics critical for precision medicine. This study introduces a PINN framework specifically tailored for spectral CT data to estimate parameters such as density, effective atomic number, and tissue stopping power, which are vital for optimizing particle therapy treatments.

The choice of PINNs is based on their ability to integrate known physical laws into the learning process, constraining the solution space to physically plausible outputs. This enhances the network's predictive accuracy and generalizability across different body tissues and imaging conditions. In spectral CT, where data is rich but complex due to the energy-dependent attenuation profiles, PINNs effectively utilize the underlying physics of X-ray attenuation to disentangle these profiles into clinically useful quantitative outputs.

Our approach involves training the PINN using a combination of spectral CT datasets and simulated data that spans a range of clinically relevant scenarios. The network architecture is designed to explicitly incorporate physical equations relating X-ray attenuation with tissue properties, facilitated by a novel loss function that penalizes deviations from physical laws.

Initial results show that the proposed PINN model outperforms traditional machine learning techniques in accuracy and robustness, validating its effectiveness in extracting critical parameters from spectral CT data. Furthermore, by providing more accurate measurements of tissue stopping power, the model significantly enhances the precision of particle therapy planning.

Technology Briefings - Serbia Session

Agenda

Time: 10:15-12:30, September 12 (Thursday), 2024 Venue: 3/F Meeting Room 7, Asia Pacific Tower, Jinling Hotel Facilitator: Mr. Nedeljko Milosavljević, Independent Expert Associate, Department of Science, University of Belgrade, Co-founder of EPI CENTER

10:15-10:25	Address, Introduction of Agenda and Presenters by the Facilitator
Section I	Addresses
10:25-10:30	Address by Mr. Wu Le, Deputy Director, Productivity Centre of Jiangsu Province
Section II	Technology Roadshows by Representatives from CEECs
10:30-10:40	Mr. Saša Radovanović, Director, Institute for Medical Research, University of Belgrade
10:40-10:50	Ms. Marijana Skorić, Senior Assistant Research Fellow, Institute for Biological Research“ Siniša Stanković”
10:50-11:00	Ms. Danijela Vojnovic Milutinovic, Principal Research Fellow, Institute for Biological Research“ Siniša Stanković”
11:00-11:10	Mr. Marko Džombić, Co-founder & CEO, K-EoP Protocol
11:10-11:20	Mr. Ilija Veljkovic, CMO, Petsie and Neo Pill
11:20-11:30	Mr. Đorđe Zdravković, Co-founder & CEO, Protokol.io
11:30-11:40	Mr. Milos Lukic, CEO, ReadyCMS
11:40-11:50	Mr. Stevan Vrbaški, Research Assistant, Department of General Educational Subjects, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad
11:50-12:00	Mr. Stefan Mrvaljevic, Co-founder & CEO, VirtuLearn.AI
Section III	Innovative Cooperation Demands Releasing by Jiangsu Institutions
12:00-12:15	Ms. Yang Guoyi, Director of China Merchants Fourth Bureau, Life Science & Health Industry Office Administrative Committee of Nanjing Jiangbei New Area
Section IV	Interaction
12:15-12:30	Q&A

Invitation

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Name: Mr. Stevan Vrbaški

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Title: Post-doc & Teaching Assistant & CEO

Organization: Department of General Education Subjects, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad;
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Dear Mr. Stevan Vrbaški

The China-CEEC Conference on Technology Cooperation and Exchange is a mechanism-based event aimed at deepening long-term innovation collaboration between China and Central and Eastern European Countries (CEECs). Since 2022, two Conferences have been successfully held and well received by attendees from both China and CEECs. To further facilitate the exchanges and innovation cooperation between China and CEECs, the 3rd Conference hosted by China-CEEC Technology Transfer Centre (Jiangsu S&T Exchange Center with Foreign Countries) will be held from September 10 to 14, 2024 in Nanjing, Jiangsu.

To highlight industry-university-research cooperation and matchmaking, the Conference this year will be renamed as "2024 China-CEEC Conference on Industry-University-Research Cooperation and Exchange". The Conference includes the plenary session, technology briefing sessions, B2B meetings, and site visits in Jiangsu for representatives from CEECs.

Program

September 10 (Tuesday)

Registration (All day)

September 11 (Wednesday)

Activities of 2024 Jiangsu Conference on Industry-University-Research Cooperation and Exchange (All Day)

September 12 (Thursday)

Plenary Session of 2024 China-CEEC Conference on Industry-University-Research Cooperation and Exchange (09:00-10:00)

Technology Briefing Sessions (10:15-12:15)

B2B Meetings (14:00-17:00)

September 13-14 (Friday-Saturday)

Site Visits in Jiangsu for Representatives from CEECs (All day)

On behalf of the China-CEEC Technology Transfer Center, I cordially invite you to be a guest speaker at the Technology Briefing Session. Given your distinguished expertise and substantial contributions to academic research and technology transfer, we believe that your presence and insights would greatly enrich the experience for our attendees. Your keynote speech on "Physics-Informed Neural Networks for Quantitative Analysis of Medical CT scans" would provide valuable perspectives and inspire our diverse audience. We note that you will be responsible for all costs incurred during the visit including airfare, local transport and accommodation. Looking forward to seeing you among our honorable guests.

Ms. ZHOU Qiuping

Executive Director

China-CEEC Technology Transfer Centre (CCTTC)

Jiangsu S&T Exchange Center with Foreign Countries

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